

The Role of GGBFS as a Promoter for Un-Calcined Kaolinite Based (Hydrosodalite Based) Geopolymer

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Abstract— *Un-calcined kaolinite based (hydrosodalite based) geopolymers are good candidate as a green building material. Its higher productivity with heat curing method promising for widening industrial applications. The main drawback of these materials is their low strength. In this study high reactive ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) blended with kaolinite up to 40 wt.%. Compressive strength, behavior against water, phase structure and microstructure of the samples were investigated systematically. It's clear from the results that GGBFS is very good candidate to enhance this type of green materials in industrial applications. GGBFS enhanced mechanical properties and behavior against the water of the sample significantly. Optimum compressive strength obtained was 11.2 MPa at 20 wt.% GGBFS addition, while reference samples recorded as 3.1 MPa.*

Keywords— *Hydrosodalite, Geopolymer, Green Materials, Kaolin, Sustainable Production*

I. INTRODUCTION

Global warming and climate change due to the CO₂ emission is currently one of the most important issues in the world[1]. One important source of CO₂ emission is from ordinary Portland cement (OPC) production[1],[2]. In the process of OPC production, the CO₂ emission comes mainly from two parts: the raw materials decomposition and the fuel burning. CO₂ emission from the production of cement was reported to consist of 5–7% of global total CO₂ emission[3],[4],[5], it is estimated that every ton of cement produces around one ton of CO₂, a major greenhouse gas implicated in global warming [6],[7],[8],[9]. How to reduce the CO₂ emission and energy cost during cement production has become an urgent question for researchers to explore further. Many researches worked on developing new alternative materials to OPC in aiming of minimizing the needs of OPC and its negative effects. Alkali activated materials, geopolymer and inorganic polymer were extensively studied as comparative and competitive materials to OPC due to its clean impact on environment, these modern materials have exhibited an excellent mechanical properties

and resistance to fire and acids [10],[11],[12],[13],[14]. In general, these techniques involved mixing materials characterized rich in alumina, silica and calcium with alkaline solution as activator. The solid part involved precursor such as slag, fly ash, metakaolin, kaolin and waste materials [15]. Kaolin is highly important for industry, especially due to its specific properties that benefit a large number of applications [16],[17]. Industrially, kaolin is a clay composed mainly of kaolinite or other related clay minerals[18]. Kaolin essentially comprised of silica, alumina and water in variable combinations [19]. Kaolin characterized by low reactivity in alkali activation [20]. Therefore, thermal or mechanical treatment may applied to increase its reactivity [21],[22], but these treatment still requiring further energy, time and money[23], as well as sophisticated appliance.

Recently, there are many laboratories working on developing new routes to use natural kaolinite without pre-treatment, Rahier et al. [15] produced building materials by activated kaolinite by NaOH solution in present of silica sand. Ehab et al. [24] studied the formation of metal oxide-based hydroxysodalite by alkali-activation of kaolinite with four metal oxides. Housni et al. [25] investigate the influence of the alkaline activator concentration of kaolin-based geopolymers on the compressive strength at the curing early age 24 h. and 3 days ageing. Marsh et al. [26] using kaolinite activated by NaOH solution at workability consistent with extrusion to synthesis hydrosodalite. Heah et al [27] studied the effect of curing process on kaolin based geopolymer with NaOH and water glass. According to many researchers, the alkali activation of natural kaolinite using NaOH commonly produces hydrosodalite [11],[21],[28].

Although their low cost and low CO₂ emission, low reaction kinetic and low mechanical properties are the major problem of kaolinite based geopolymer. Possible synergy between the low reactive kaolinite and highly reactive calcium and alumina

silicate bearing GGBFS seems suitable solution to obtain acceptable reactivity in blended precursor. In this study it was investigated that the addition of GGBFS to heat cured kaolinite based (hydrosodalite based) geopolymer to overcome the low mechanical properties of final product for various applications such as green building materials.

II. EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

A) Materials

High purity kaolin used as the first source of aluminosilicate. Kaolin particles size characterized by 93% of bulk volume below 2 μm . Chemical Composition (wt.%) of the kaolin and GGBFS are given in Tab.1. GGBFS particles size of $D_{(0.5)}$ is 13,5 μm . NaOH sodium hydroxide pellet of Merck brand with 99 wt.% and distilled water were used to prepared activator solution.

B) Samples Preparation

To produce samples, kaolinite powder mixed in solid state with GGBFS until completely homogenization observed. Additives added in four percentages 10, 20, 30 and 40wt.% for optimization purpose. In other side, alkali activator synthesized by mixing NaOH pellets with distilled water in amount of 70wt.% of kaolinite weight; mixing process done in plastic-tightly closed bottle to avoid evaporation during exothermal reaction. The selection of plastic-material bottle rather than glass was to avoid interaction between solution and glass. NaOH pellet was fixed at 24wt.% of kaolinite weight. After alkali activator cooled and reached room temperature, solid and liquid parts mixed together by using electrical mixer for 5 minutes. Samples extruded into cylindrical shape (1 cm diameter and 2 cm height). The plastic extruded samples immediately place in open ventilated oven and dried at 150°C for 2 h. After that samples leaved to cool, and then mechanical and analytical test conducted. For comparison, reference samples would be produced by similar route explained above, except additive materials will not be used in reference samples.

C) Characterization

The compressive strength test conducted by a Zwick / Roell 600 kN capacity test device at a constant speed of 1.00 mm / min. The highest strength achieved until the samples were damaged was recorded. The experiments were conducted on three samples and the average values were considered. Water absorption and weight loss test would be conducted, the samples weigh immediately after removed from oven, dry-weight was denoted by (W_i), then samples soaked in water for up to 7 days then samples removed from water and weigh it again, the recorded weights denoted by (W_s). The percentage of water absorption is calculated by the equation below for the first 24 hr.

$$\% \text{ Water absorption} = ((W_s - W_i) / W_i) * 100 \quad (1)$$

To measure weight loss percentage after water immersion, samples that removed from water vessels will be heated in oven at 150°C for 2 hours after that samples will weighing and

TABLE 1
COMPOSITION OF KAOLIN AND GGBFS

Chemical Composition (wt.%)		
Oxides	Kaolin	GGBFS
Al ₂ O ₃	36.9	11.1
SiO ₂	46.1	37.1
SO ₃	0.5	1.6
K ₂ O	1.07	1.4
CaO	0.03	38.9
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.6	0.7
MgO	-	4.9
L.O.I	12.75	-

the values will denoted by W_f . The percentages of weight loss by water immersion or leaching were measured from equation below for up to 7 days of immersion.

$$\% \text{ Weight loss} = ((W_i - W_f) / W_i) * 100 \quad (2)$$

RIGAKU ULTRA IV XRD device was used for X-Ray Diffraction analyses. The analysis ranges were 5 to 70 degree and analyze rate is 5%/minute. SEM analyses were performed with CARL ZEISS ULTRA PLUS GEMINI FESEM device. Samples were coated with gold to obtain conductivity before tests.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A) Compressive Strength Result

The result of compressive strength test proved a significant role to GGBFS additives in comparison with reference samples which doesn't contain GGBFS additives. In comparison with certain previous research that used un-calcined kaolinite as a main source of aluminosilicate [20],[27],[29],[30],[31], current result was the comparable or better. The samples 20wt.% additives showed the highest compressive strength, it's reached 11.20 MPa, after which the strength was gradually decreased with increment in GGBFS additive. The lowest compressive strength obtained from 10wt.% additives was 3.4 MPa, and this value is approximately near to the value of reference samples which haven't any additive (Fig. 1). This closeness in compressive strength values between 10wt.%GGBFS and reference samples referred to the 10% of GGBFS is not sufficient to support reaction with abundant reactive molecules, while the samples of 30 and 40wt.% additives present a drop from the values recorded at 20wt.%. These decreasing in values of 30 and 40wt.% GGBFS may be related to remaining amount of un reacted precursor

which are formed when cation of activator solution consumed completely in the reaction by more reactive GGBFS.

Panagiotopoulou et al.[32] studied the effect of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio of GGBFS based alkali activation; they reported the optimum ratio of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is 3.5. The different point of the samples produced in this study was not mix with sodium silicate solution to feed the system with high viscosity sodium silicate to support the hydrosodalite crystallization. By this way a negative effect of low Si/Al ratio in compressive strength will going on, but it is turn into advantage in production; thus, the lack of sodium silicate solution in precursor was allow to bring into action of rapid curing approach. Regarding to kaolinite, Slaty et al.[33] optimizing the effect of NaOH % by kaolinite clay weight in presence of sand, they found the optimum ratio of NaOH was gain at 16% by weight of kaolinite clay in fixed water percentage of 22% by kaolinite clay weight. The concentration of activator solution used in these experiments is somehow lower than activator used by Slaty et al.[33].

Fig.1 Compressive strength results. Ref; reference samples

B) Durability Result

The samples exhibited good result for weight loss percentage throughout 7 days of immersion (Fig. 2). The percentages of weight loss were start increasing in a regular manner with time passed (from 1 day up to 7 days). The lower weight loss percentage was recorded for 20wt.% GGBFS samples after 1 day of soaking in water, the value was 2.27wt.%, and this good result appear agreed with compressive strength result of same samples, that's may attributed to the high amount of reacted materials. The higher weight loss percentages was 4.95wt.%, its recorded for 10wt.% additives samples after 7 days of soaking, whereas reference samples shown 7.05% of weight loss after 7 days. The difference in weight loss percentage between reference samples and GGBFS added samples are clearly proved the deeply influence of GGBFS additives on alkali activated kaolinite. Yip et al. [34]who studying the durability of kaolinite and GGBFS mixture, proposed that the presence of amorphous zeolitic phase and geopolymeric gel are responsible to the good

durability and also they attributed the durability of ancient heritage to the presence of zeolitic materials, also, Campell et al. [35] report: the good durability of ancient binder attributed to zeolitic structure formed. Fig.3 showed inverse relationship between GGBFS addition and water absorption; consequently, water absorption percentages are gradually decreased from reference samples to 40wt.% additives including sample, that's leading to find the open porosity of samples decreasing with increasing GGBFS addition.

Fig.2 wt.% of weight loss percentage.REF ; reference samples

Fig.3 wt.% of water absorption percentage.REF; reference samples

C) XRD Result

XRD pattern of the kaolinite and produced samples are given in Fig.4. XRD analyses showed developing of new peaks after alkali activation process besides the kaolinite peaks related to main precursor. These new peaks corresponded for hydrosodalite phases. The growing of these new peaks synchronized with degradation in intensities of kaolinite peaks, this was attributed to the dissolution of kaolinite as much as hydrosodalite formed and this observation agrees with Marsh et al. [26],[36].The low peaks intensities of hydrosodalite might be corresponded to the low reactivity of kaolinite which retain on its appearance even in further stages, and that may be interpreted as partial dissolution of kaolinite and consequently

partials contribution in reaction, this justification was adopted by many researchers [37],[38],[39],[40]. The XRD peaks of samples with additives showed changing in the crystal structure into more amorphous structure in comparison with reference samples; this was observed by the widening of the peaks and the weakening of the intensity. Many research confirmed the formation of CSH phase from GGBFS alkali Activation [41],[42],[43],[44], in these experiments, the additives materials did not show a formation of any other zeolite phase (when incorporated with kaolinite) differ from phases observed in reference samples, that may interpreted as; the additives materials were dissolve in NaOH solution leading to SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and CaO abundant in the mixture related to their chemistry.

Fig.4 XRD pattern of the samples, K ; kaolinite , HS ; Hydrosodalite

Fig.5 XRD of reference and 20% additives samples. HS ;hydrosodalite , K; kaolinite.

D) SEM Result

SEM photos showed evidence refer to hydrosodalite phase formation; these evidences were varied according to the additive's percentage. In SEM photo, plate-like particles refer to kaolinite, but spheroidal-shape particle refer to hydrosodalite [26]. In addition to more compact microstructure due to incorporation of GGBFS to matrix as an amorphous phase, additives samples present good signs which assuring the occurrence of crystallization with performance better than crystals found in reference samples, thus the difference was noticeable between SEM photo of reference samples and additive samples (Fig.5). 20wt.% additives including samples were the best among all GGBFS-additive samples in terms of hydrosodalite formations, these results are matching with high compressive strength of 20wt.%.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study influence of the GGBFS addition to kaolin based (hydrosodalite based) geopolymer synthesis studied systematically. Results showed that GGBFS addition wt.%20 enhanced the compressive strength of the product significantly. With the 20wt.%GGBFS addition compressive strength of the reference sample increased to 11.2 MPa from 3.1 MPa. GGBFS addition also enhances the water resistant of the samples. Water absorption of the samples decreased with increasing GGBFS addition. Phase analyses showed that the hydrosodalite formation at the samples. With increasing GGBFS addition amorphousness increased. This is a sign of feeding geopolymeric unit to kaolin based geopolymer originated from alkali degradation of GGBFS. Obtaining molded alumina silicates without elevated heat treatments by using natural ores with a byproduct of iron and steel industry make this material more sustainable than portland cement-based and fired clay-based alternatives. There is need for new studies on testing of the binder in production of environmentally friendly building materials such as bricks, insulation boards and fire-resistant claddings.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We acknowledge the Karabuk University, Turkey. This work was supported by Karabuk University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit under the project number (FYL-2020-2292).

REFERENCES

- [1]. M. Schneider, M. Romer, M. Tschudin, and H. Bolio, "Sustainable cement production—present and future," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 41, pp. 642–650, Jul. 2011.
- [2]. E. Benhelal, G. Zahedi, E. Shamsaei, and A. Bahadori, "Global strategies and potentials to curb CO₂ emissions in cement industry," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 51, pp. 142–161, Jul. 2013.
- [3]. E. Gartner, "Industrially interesting approaches to 'low-CO₂' cements," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 34, pp. 1489–1498, Sep. 2004.
- [4]. H. D. Matthews, N. P. Gillett, P. A. Stott, and K. Zickfeld, "The proportionality of global warming to cumulative carbon emissions," *Nature*, vol. 459, pp. 829–832, Jun. 2009.
- [5]. E. Worrell, L. Price, N. Martin, C. Hendriks, and L. O. Meida, "Carbon dioxide emissions from the global cement industry," *Annu. Rev. energy Environ.*, vol. 26, pp. 303–329, Nov. 2001.
- [6]. Y. Kim and E. Worrell, "CO₂ emission trends in the cement industry: An international comparison," *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Chang.*, vol. 7, pp. 115–133, Jun. 2002.
- [7]. B. Lothenbach, K. Scrivener, and R. D. Hooton, "Supplementary cementitious materials," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 41, pp. 1244–1256, Dec. 2011.
- [8]. M. Taylor, C. Tam, and D. Gielen, "Energy efficiency and CO₂ emissions from the global cement industry," *Korea*, vol. 50, pp. 61–67, Sep. 2006.
- [9]. T. A. Boden, G. Marland, and R. J. Andres, "Global, regional, and national fossil-fuel CO₂ emissions," *Carbon dioxide Inf. Anal. center, Oak ridge Natl. Lab. US Dep. energy, Oak Ridge, Tenn., USA* doi, vol. 10, 2009.
- [10]. S. A. Bernal and J. L. Provis, "Durability of alkali-activated materials: progress and perspectives," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 97, pp. 997–1008, Apr. 2014.
- [11]. J. Davidovits, "Geopolymers: inorganic polymeric new materials," *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, vol. 37, pp. 1633–1656, Aug. 1991.
- [12]. P. Duxson, J. L. Provis, G. C. Lukey, and J. S. J. Van Deventer, "The role of inorganic polymer technology in the development of 'green concrete,'" *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 37, pp. 1590–1597, Dec. 2007.
- [13]. H. Rahier, B. Van Mele, M. Biesemans, J. Wastiels, and X. Wu, "Low-temperature synthesized aluminosilicate glasses," *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 31, pp. 71–79, Jan. 1996.
- [14]. H. Xu and J. S. J. Van Deventer, "The geopolymerisation of aluminosilicate minerals," *Int. J. Miner. Process.*, vol. 59, pp. 247–266, Jun. 2000.
- [15]. H. Rahier, M. Esaifan, J. Wastiels, F. Slatyi, I. Aldabsheh, and H. Khoury, "Alkali activation of kaolinite for production of bricks and tiles," *In Proc. Non-Traditional Cem. Concr. IV*, 2011, vol. 4, p. 162.
- [16]. H. H. Murray, "Traditional and new applications for kaolin, smectite, and palygorskite: a general overview," *Appl. Clay Sci.*, vol. 17, pp. 207–221, Nov. 2000.
- [17]. P. A. Schroeder and G. Erickson, "Kaolin: From ancient porcelains to nanocomposites," *Elements*, vol. 10, pp. 177–182, Jun. 2014.
- [18]. M. Garcia-Valles, P. Alfonso, S. Martínez, and N. Roca, "Mineralogical and thermal characterization of kaolinitic clays from Terra Alta (Catalonia, Spain)," *Minerals*, vol. 10, p. 142–157, Feb. 2020.
- [19]. Y. H. Cheng, K. Hazlinda, A. Mohd Mustafa Al-Bakri, M. Luqman, K. Nizar, and Y. M. Liew, "Potential application of kaolin without calcine as greener concrete: a review," *Aust. J. Basic & Appl. Sci.*, vol. 5, p. 1026–1035, Jul. 2011.
- [20]. C. Y. Heah, K. Hussin, M. M. Al Bakri Abdullah, M. Bnhussain, L. Musa, I. Khairul Nizar, C. M. R. Ghazali, and Y. M. Liew, "Strength and microstructural properties of mechanically-activated kaolin geopolymers," *in Advanced Materials Research*, 2013, vol. 626, pp. 926–930. Dec. 2012.
- [21]. A. Á. B. Maia, R. F. Neves, R. S. Angélica, and H. Pöllmann, "Synthesis of sodalite from Brazilian kaolin wastes," *Clay Miner.*, vol. 50, pp. 663–675, Dec. 2015.
- [22]. J. L. Provis and J. S. J. Van Deventer, *Alkali activated materials: state-of-the-art report, RILEM TC 224-AAM*. Springer Dordrecht Heidelberg New York London, 2013.
- [23]. R. Fernandez, F. Martirena, and K. L. Scrivener, "The origin of the pozzolanic activity of calcined clay minerals: A comparison between kaolinite, illite and montmorillonite," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 41, pp. 113–122, Jan. 2011.
- [24]. E. AlShamaileh, M. Esaifan, and Q. Abu-Afifeh, "Formation of metal oxide-based hydroxysodalite by alkali-activation of kaolinite," *Chemija*, vol. 31, pp. 130–136, Jul. 2020.
- [25]. A. D. Hounsi, G. Lecomte-Nana, G. Djeteli, P. Blanchart, D. Alowanou, P. Kpelou, K. Napo, G. Tchangbedji, and M. Praisler, "How does Na, K alkali metal concentration change the early age structural characteristic of kaolin-based geopolymers," *Ceram. Int.*, vol. 40, pp. 8953–8962, Aug. 2014.
- [26]. A. Marsh, A. Heath, P. Patureau, M. Evernden, and P. Walker, "A mild conditions synthesis route to produce hydrosodalite from kaolinite, compatible with extrusion processing," *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.*, vol. 264, pp. 125–132, Jul. 2018.
- [27]. C. Y. Heah, H. Kamarudin, A. M. Al Bakri, M. Binhussain, L. Musa, I. Khairul Nizar, C. M. R. Ghazali, and Y. M. Liew, "Curing behavior on kaolin-based geopolymers," *in Proc. Advanced Materials Research*, 2012, vol. 548, p. 42.
- [28]. M. Esaifan, H. Rahier, A. Barhoum, H. Khoury, M. Hourani, and J. Wastiels, "Development of inorganic polymer by alkali-activation of untreated kaolinitic clay: Reaction stoichiometry, strength and dimensional stability," *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 91, pp. 251–259, Aug. 2015.
- [29]. C. Y. Heah, H. Kamarudin, M. M. Al Bakri Abdullah, M. Binhussain, L. Musa, I. Khairul Nizar, C. M. R. Ghazali, and Y. M. Liew, "Effect of mechanical activation on kaolin-based geopolymers," *in Proc. Advanced Materials Research*, 2012, vol. 479, p. 357.
- [30]. C. Y. Heah, H. Kamarudin, A. M. M. Al Bakri, M. Bnhussain, M. Luqman, I. K. Nizar, C. M. Ruzaiddi, and Y. M. Liew, "Study on solids-to-liquid and alkaline activator ratios on kaolin-based geopolymers," *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 35, pp. 912–922, Oct. 2012.
- [31]. C. Y. Heah, H. Kamarudin, A. Mohd Mustafa Al-Bakri, B. Mohamed, M. Luqman, K. Nizar, and Y. M. Liew, "Effect of alkali concentration on mechanical properties of kaolin geopolymers," *Romanian Journal of Materials*, vol. 42, pp. 179–186, Apr. 2012.
- [32]. C. Panagiotopoulou, G. Kakali, S. Tsvivilis, T. Perraki, and M. Perraki, "Synthesis and characterisation of slag based geopolymers," *in Proc. Materials science forum*, 2010, vol. 636, p. 155.
- [33]. F. Slatyi, H. Khoury, J. Wastiels, and H. Rahier, "Characterization of alkali activated kaolinitic clay," *Appl. Clay Sci.*, vol. 75, pp. 120–125, May. 2013.

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- [34]. C. K. Yip and J. S. J. Van Deventer, "Microanalysis of calcium silicate hydrate gel formed within a geopolymeric binder," *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 38, pp. 3851–3860, Sep. 2003.
- [35]. D. H. Campbell and R. L. Folk, "Ancient Egyptian Pyramids--Concrete or Rock," *Concr. Int.*, vol. 13, pp. 28–30, Aug. 1991.
- [36]. A. Marsh, A. Heath, P. Patureau, M. Evernden, and P. Walker, "Stabilisation of clay mixtures and soils by alkali activation," in *Proce. International Symposium on Earthen Structures*, 2019, p. 15
- [37]. J. L. Provis, C. Z. Yong, P. Duxson, and J. S. J. van Deventer, "Correlating mechanical and thermal properties of sodium silicate-fly ash geopolymers," *Colloids Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.*, vol. 336, pp. 57–63, Mar. 2009.
- [38]. Z. Zuhua, Y. Xiao, Z. Huajun, and C. Yue, "Role of water in the synthesis of calcined kaolin-based geopolymer," *Appl. Clay Sci.*, vol. 43, pp. 218–223, Feb. 2009.
- [39]. M. S. Prasad, K. J. Reid, and H. H. Murray, "Kaolin: processing, properties and applications," *Appl. Clay Sci.*, vol. 6, pp. 87–119, Sep. 1991.
- [40]. Y. M. Liew, H. Kamarudin, A. M. M. Al Bakri, M. Bnhussain, M. Luqman, I. K. Nizar, C. M. Ruzaidi, and C. Y. Heah, "Optimization of solids-to-liquid and alkali activator ratios of calcined kaolin geopolymeric powder," *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 37, pp. 440–451, Dec. 2012.
- [41]. C. Shi, X. Wu, and M. Tang, "Hydration of alkali-slag cements at 150 C," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 21, pp. 91–100, Jan. 1991.
- [42]. S.-D. Wang and K. L. Scrivener, "Hydration products of alkali activated slag cement," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 25, pp. 561–571, Apr. 1995.
- [43]. Z. Pan, L. Cheng, Y. Lu, and N. Yang, "Hydration products of alkali-activated slag–red mud cementitious material," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 32, pp. 357–362, Mar. 2002.
- [44]. Z. Pan, D. Li, J. Yu, and N. Yang, "Properties and microstructure of the hardened alkali-activated red mud–slag cementitious material," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 33, pp. 1437–1441, Sep. 2003.